

March 25, 2024

Press release

On March 22nd, 2024, ENEA, in collaboration with the CST4ALL consortium, hosted a successful online workshop on the R&I challenges for the hybridization of CST with other renewable energy technologies.

Over 160 participants from research, industry and governmental organizations joined the two sessions of the workshop, delving into key research areas in the development of hybrid CST systems.

Elisabeth Schellmann (European Commission, DG Energy) welcomed the participants and acknowledged the importance of the event. She pointed out that keeping the manufacturing of renewable energy technologies within the EU is a core priority for the Commission, as shown by the Net Zero Industry Act, and this is even more important for CST technologies, for which EU still holds technological leadership.

The first technical session, moderated by Luca Turchetti (ENEA, Italy) focused on components and technological interfaces that enable the physical connection between different renewable energy technologies, featuring presentations from representatives of Exheat group (UK), Magaldi Power (Italy), CIEMAT (Spain), ODTÜ–GÜNAM (Türkiye) and DLR (Germany). Alex Ellis (Exheat group), and Carla Bevilacqua (Magaldi Power) showcased relevant industrial cases of development of Electrical heaters specifically designed for heat transfer fluids and heat storage media used in commercial and emerging CST plant configurations, like molten salts and fluidized particle beds. Margarita Rodriguez (CIEMAT) explored microwave heating of molten salts as a non-conventional approach that can potentially overcome power limitations of Joule heating systems. A different perspective was offered by Moritz Ruhwedel (DLR) and Elsen Aydin (ODTÜ–GÜNAM), who showed results in the development of hybrid concentrating solar thermal – (concentrating) photovoltaic collectors, offering a different approach to system integration.

The second session, moderated by Marco Binotti (Politecnico di Milano, Italy) explored tools and strategies for optimizing the operation of hybrid plants, with presentations from KTH (Sweden), TSK-Flagsol (Germany), METU (Türkiye), DLR (Germany) and ENEA (Italy).

An overview of the latest trends in the development of hybrid plants was provided by Raphael Guedez (KTH), who showed how the interest in hybrid system is expanding beyond power generation, to include industrial heat applications and benefits are especially significant for baseload applications with capacity factors above 60%. Ybekal Gedle (TSK-Flagsol) building on the experience of his company in the development of one of world's first commercial hybrid CST-CSP projects in Morocco, showed that hybrid CSP-PV plants can achieve a lower LCOE, but great attention should be devoted to financing parameters, choice of subsystems and operational strategy. Juergen Dersch (DLR) highlighted the challenges in the optimization of hybrid plants, which start with the very definition of the optimization objectives and include dealing with significant computational burden, even if simplified approaches allow to achieve satisfactory results with manageable simulation times and deviations below 4%.

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the European Union**

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Bertuğ Çelebi (METU) focused on the hybridization of CST with biomass, showing the advantages of hybrid systems in terms of increased capacity of the biomass plant (+20%), better flexibility and reduced specific operational costs, while identifying challenges in high capital costs and availability of suitable plant locations, due to the features required by both technologies and competition with the use of fertile lands. The technical panel was closed by Raffaele Liberatore (ENEA), who showed how combination of CST and PV can also improve the cost effectiveness of alternative renewable hydrogen production processes, by combining the advantages of long-term thermal energy storage of CST systems with the cheap renewable electricity prices offered by PV.

Overall, this second session showed that, despite the increased complexity, hybrid plants can offer improved techno-economic performance and flexibility, which can contribute to the development of more sustainable and resilient energy systems.

This workshop provided valuable insights for researchers and industry professionals working on advancing hybrid CST technologies.

CST4ALL Coordinator

**Deutsches Zentrum
für Luft- und Raumfahrt e.V.**
in der Helmholtz-Gemeinschaft

DLR: Deutsches Zentrum fuer Luft - Und Raumfahrt EV (DE)

CST4ALL Partners

CIEMAT: Centro de Investigaciones Energeticas,
Medioambientales y Tecnologicas (ES)

ENEA: Agenzia nazionale per le nuove tecnologie, l'energia e lo
sviluppo economico sostenibile (IT)

ESTELA: European Solar Thermal Electricity Association (BE)

GUNAM: Center for Solar Energy Research and Applications
(TR)

The CST4ALL project is committed to catalysing an array of hybridisation and cooperation initiatives at the interface between CST and other renewable energy technologies targeting the electricity, heat, and fuels sectors.

To stay up-to-date on CST4ALL's activities and opportunities, follow-us on:

- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/cst4all/>
- X (formerly Twitter): <https://twitter.com/Cst4All>
- Website: <https://cst4all.eu/en/>

You can also sign-up for the **CST4ALL Newsletter** to receive updates on other project events and outputs through the following link: <https://cst4all.eu/en/4169-contact-connect>.

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